

The production and perception of phrase prominence in pre-schoolers from Stockholm and Scania

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Abstract

The use of phrase-level prosodic prominence (PLP) relations for the encoding of information structure (IS) is mastered fairly late in children's language development according to previous research (e.g., MacWhinney & Bates, 1978; de Ruiter, 2010). However, few studies have investigated children's production of PLP in relation to how they perceive and comprehend PLP in the context of IS encoding and decoding (Chen, 2010); earlier studies involving perception have made use of offline paradigms (e.g., Wells et al., 2004), while more recent studies using online methods such as eye tracking have usually not been complemented by production data (e.g., Ito, 2014). In addition, previous production work has indicated that language-specific intonational-phonological properties of PLP might play a role, too (e.g., Romøren & Chen, 2015, 2021; Prieto & Esteve-Gibert, 2018). In this study we explore the production and perception of PLP as used to mark contrastive focus in 3–5-year-old children speaking either Scanian or Stockholm Swedish, two dialects which differ crucially in the way PLP is realized phonetically. While both dialects exhibit a lexical accent contrast, PLP is realized more subtle in the Scanian variety: instead of adding a prominence H(igh)-tone, PLP is encoded through phonetic adjustments of the H(igh)L(ow) accent patterns determined by the lexical accent. Our production experiment involves eliciting adjective-noun phrases displaying different PLP relations (e.g., 'a red BOAT' vs. 'a RED boat'), using an interactive video/card game. Production data are analysed acoustically and auditorily. In our visual-word eye-tracking experiment we use the same pictures of coloured objects to investigate whether children make use of PLP relations in the audio stimuli for reference resolution. Preliminary results suggest that 5-year-olds from Stockholm display a perception behaviour like adults; in 3–4-year-olds, this pattern is emerging. For Scanian children (3–5 years), we cannot observe any sensitivity for PLP yet.

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